

A working group for hybrid rice has been formed with a plant breeder, seed production specialist, and plant pathologist and entomologist. This program involves collaborative research with the Bangladesh Agricultural Develop-

ment Corporation, and other public and private agencies engaged in seed production in the country. A specific, time-bound, and goal-oriented work plan has been made for developing hybrid rice technology for the boro

season. Routine evaluation of elite lines and introduced rice hybrids is continuing. Four hybrid combinations were found promising and these hybrids are undergoing on-farm trials. ■

Grain quality

Donors for quality traits from the international aromatic nursery

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To identify some varieties with basmati background to be used as donors, the first International Fine Grain Aromatic Rice Observational Nursery (IRFAON), consisting of 33 entries including the international check Basmati 370 along with local check Pusa Basmati 1, was grown under normal cultural practices during the 1996 wet season. All the varieties were analyzed for 14 physicochemical characteristics at the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, using standard procedures. These characteristics involve grain size and shape, endosperm appearance, and milling and head rice recovery (HRR). Among the cooking and eating quality traits, water uptake (WU), volume expansion ratio (VER), kernel length after cooking (KLAC), elongation ratio (ER), gelatinization temperature (GT), and amylose (AC) content were studied.

Of the entries tested, 22 belonged to long slender, 5 to long bold, 2 to medium slender, and 3 to short bold groups (Table 1) (see figure). In the long slender group, DR28 (7.38 mm), DR29 (7.37 mm), and Shah Pasand (7.35 mm) recorded high kernel length. Sixteen varieties showed >60% head rice, ranging from 60% (PK1656-48-2-2-1) to 69.7% (ARC11554). Among these entries, Basmati 385 and Shah Pasand exhibited high KLAC and ER, comparable with those of the checks. Basmati 385 recorded 14.5 mm KLAC and an

elongation ratio of 2.15 and Shah Pasand exhibited 14.2 mm KLAC and an elongation ratio of 1.93. Other entries that possessed moderate to high

KLAC combined with moderate ER were Binam, Domsiah, DR28, DR29, PK1379-9-1-1, PK1399-12-1-1, and Super Basmati.

Number of entries promising for key quality traits, 1996 wet season.

Table 1. Number of entries identified as promising for key quality traits, 1996 wet season.

Category	Number	Quality traits		
		Head rice recovery (>60%)	Intermediate gelatinization temperature	Intermediate amylose content (%)
Long slender	23	9	3	9
Long bold	5	3	1	4
Medium slender	2	2	1	1
Short bold	3	2	1	3
Total	33	16	6	17

Table 2. Summary of grain quality characteristics of promising varieties in the International Fine Grain Aromatic Rice Observational Nursery, 1996 wet season.

Variety	Origin	HRR ^a (%)	KL (mm)	L/B	Alk val.	WU (mL)	VER	KLAC (mm)	ER	AC (%)	Scent	Grn. chalk
<i>Long slender group</i>												
DR28	Pakistan	61.0	7.38	3.53	7.0, 7.0	310	4.0	13.2	1.82	26.1	3	VOC
DR31	Pakistan	61.8	6.88	3.31	7.0, 7.0	230	3.8	11.3	1.64	26.4	2	VOC
Domsiah	Iran	52.0	6.80	3.54	4.8, 5.0	290	4.7	13.2	1.94	18.2	3	VOC
PK1379-9-1-1	Pakistan	56.3	6.62	3.15	6.0, 6.0	250	4.3	13.2	1.99	19.0	3	VOC
PK165648-2-2-1	Pakistan	60.0	6.50	3.16	7.0, 7.0	270	4.3	12.2	1.88	22.6	2	A
DM 38	Pakistan	64.2	6.53	3.27	3.1, 3.1	130	4.0	12.1	1.85	21.4	3	OC
<i>Long bold group</i>												
Azucena	Philippines	64.8	6.39	2.88	4.2, 3.2	130	4.0	11.3	1.77	20.9	2	OC
<i>Short bold group</i>												
ARC 11554	India	69.7	4.17	2.12	5.0, 4.3	110	4.3	7.6	1.82	21.8	2	A
Tulsimanjari 14-2	India	67.5	4.20	2.19	3.0, 3.0	100	4.3	7.9	1.88	21.0	2	A

^aHRR = head rice recovery, KL = kernel length, L/B = length/breadth, Alk val. = alkali value, WU = water uptake, VER = volume expansion ratio, KLAC = kernel length after cooking, ER = elongation ratio, AC = amylose content, scent: 3 = strong, 2 = moderate, Grn. chalk = grain chalkiness: A = absent, VOC = very occasionally present, OC = occasionally present.

Seventeen varieties had the most desirable AC range of 20-25%, and six varieties showed intermediate GT. Three varieties—ARC11554, Azucena, and Basmati 385—possessed both intermediate AC and GT. Except for PK1385-6-3-1-2, all other varieties had an aroma, which is the typical characteristic of basmati rice.

With excellent phenotypic acceptability, DR28 and DR31 (Pakistan) had >60% HRR, moderate to high KL and KLAC, and slightly higher AC (Table 2). Domsiah (Iran) was another variety that possessed all the quality traits in a desirable range, with a slightly low AC. Other varieties from Pakistan having moderate to high

HRR, KL, and KLAC coupled with good phenotypic acceptability are PK1379-9-1-1, PK1756-49-2-2-1, and DM38. With the emphasis now shifting toward the development of dwarf short-grained aromatic rice for domestic and export purposes as well, Azucena, ARC 11554, and Tulsimanjari 14-2 may also be used as donors depending on the objectives. ■

Effect of bran removal on oil recovery

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For the past two decades, India has been meeting a shortage of oils by importing this commodity at extremely high costs in terms of foreign exchange. The demand for vegetable oils in the year 2000 will be 8.75 million t. To augment oil and fat resources in India, rice bran oil needs to be made available to the maximum extent.

Experiments were conducted with two popular and common varieties of parboiled rice: coarse (UPR79) and fine (Basmati) rice grown in the Tarai region of Uttar Pradesh, India. The objective of this study was to evaluate the effect of bran removal on oil recovery. Clean rice samples were collected from a commercial rice mill.

Effect of bran removal on degree of polish and oil recovery of rice bran.

Time of milling (s)	Basmati ^a			UPR79		
	D _p (%)	O _r (%)	W _g (g)	D _p (%)	O _r (%)	w _g (g)
0	0	0	0.02299	0	0	0.02145
10	3.33	15.70	0.02146	2.75	14.57	0.02054
20	3.94	18.57	0.02055	3.49	14.90	0.02032
30	5.08	19.25	0.02010	4.46	15.56	0.01962
40	6.32	19.52	0.01956	5.06	16.55	0.01732
50	7.02	20.91	0.01909	5.34	17.46	0.01730
60	7.83	20.91	0.01801	5.81	17.90	0.01676
70	8.13	19.95	0.01755	6.25	17.02	0.01615
80	8.51	19.51	0.01760	6.56	16.34	0.01610
90	8.84	18.76	0.01700	6.97	15.72	0.01600
100	8.94	17.60	0.01620	7.18	15.58	0.01536
110	9.05	17.07	0.01618	7.57	15.07	0.01480

Statistical parameters of $O_r = aD_p - bD_p^2$

Variety	a	b	r	SEE
Basmati	6.367	0.4859	0.999	0.721
UPR79	6.348	0.5822	0.991	0.699

^aD_p = degree of polish on brown rice basis, %; O_r = oil recovery of rice bran, %; W_g = weight of one grain, g; r = correlation coefficient; SEE = standard error of estimate.

The moisture content of collected samples of UPR79 and Basmati was determined by the oven method. Both varieties had an average moisture

content of about 14%. The collected rice samples were shelled and milled/polished via a Satake rice sheller and polisher. Milling time varied from 0 to